

RESEARCH ARTICLE

From Ecofeminism to Green Theory: Understanding Transnational Intersections within Nature and the Self

Rahee Dahake

PhD Research Scholar, Department of English, M.V.P. Samaj's K.R.T. Arts, B.H Commerce & A.M. Science, (KTHM) College, Nashik, India;
raheedahake@gmail.com

Dr. Sharad Binnor

Professor and Head, Department of English, M.V.P. Samaj's K.R.T. Arts, B.H Commerce & A.M. Science (KTHM) College, Nashik, India;
sharadbinnor@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the work of Autumn Peltier and Parineeta Dandekar, environmentalists working within transnational spaces of Canada and India, on the question of water. In this context, the paper attempts a reading of the Marathi novel *Nadisht*, by Manoj Borgavkar and *Surfacing* by Margaret Atwood, bringing together issues of marginalised communities, gender, ecology and the relationship with nature. Dandekar unearths stories, lore, songs and poetry that depict a connection with the river; Peltier evokes the archetypal connection within the womb. Borgavkar's novel revolves around the constructs of the mother and the river, while Atwood's protagonist grapples with separation and the rebirth of the self. These transnational intersections are examined from an ecocritical and green studies perspective, including ecofeminism and green theory. The study finds that the relationship between nature and the self, the power, inequity and domination is symbolized in the abuse of nature and questions it to bring about change.

Keywords: ecofeminism, ecocriticism, green theory, Canadian Literature

FULL RESEARCH PAPER**Introduction**

What would have been a river in 1820 is hidden behind the canopy of trees, but the gurgling sound alerts to its presence. The pulse of flowing water, mellow at times, thunderous in the monsoons, hints at the eternity of life. It washes over the ancient carved steps behind the black stone temple, smoothing them. That archetypal bond with the water is humbling. And two hundred years later, it is just a filthy stream of water. One bears witness to what could be a postmodern art installation that symbolizes disdain, neglect and abuse. What inspires anyone to humiliate that waterbody and reduce it to a state where it cannot even take with it, shreds of rags that cling to the rocks, is something incomprehensible. Is it the arrogance that the powerful possess, that hauteur which makes them feel unchallenged, as they are invisible, to pollute, to destroy?

When, in 1820, John Keats wrote the ballad 'La Belle Dame Sans Merci' containing the lines: 'The sedge has withered from the lake, / And no birds sing', he did not imagine that it would inspire a chapter in Rachel Carson's book *Silent Spring*, a book that asks us to 'foresee' and 'forestall'. In the chapter 'Surface Waters and Underground Seas', Carson alerts us to a fact that has become an undeniable reality in contemporary times: "Of all our natural resources, water has become the most precious. By far the greater part of the earth's surface is covered by its enveloping seas, yet in the midst of this plenty we are in want.... In an age when man has forgotten his origins and is blind even to his most essential needs for survival, water, along with other resources, has become the victim of his indifference." (Carson, 1962)

Shaping the Inquiry

The questions and concerns raised by Carson were relevant in 1962 and remain so today. The work done in the field of environmentalism is far-reaching. The concerns individuals face while witnessing climate change, environmental disasters and irrevocable changes in nature are the same across the world. It is in this context that it becomes significant to build connections across nations and cultures that echo one thought: one joins in the struggle towards protecting the natural environment and preserving diversity, while becoming a part of a broad ethical, social and political movement that questions and tries to reverse the damage done to the environment by human beings. This is why it is not only important to find connections across environmental movements globally, especially those that connect the global North

with the global South, but also to find connections between voices that have expressed these concerns in their texts, in the form of metaphors and narratives.

This paper examines the work of Autumn Peltier and Parineeta Dandekar, environmentalists working within the transnational spectrum, that of Canada and India, on the question of water and who, in their own spaces, come together in their understanding of the stories that represent our connection with nature through water. This paper also attempts a reading of the Indian novel *Nadisht*, written in Marathi by Manoj Borgaonkar and the novel *Surfacing* by Margaret Atwood, a Canadian novelist, which brings together issues of marginalised communities, gender and ecology by tracing the lives of the people through their relationship with nature. The work of these writers and conservationists across India and Canada unpacks themes of conservation, discrimination, exploitation of nature and oppression. This paper is an attempt to understand these transnational intersections from a green studies perspective – “a development within literary and cultural studies which is informed by the insights of ecology” (Coupe, 2013).

The term ‘ecocriticism’ is often credited to the American critic William Rueckert, who coined it in his 1978 article ‘Literature and Ecology: An Experiment in Ecocriticism’. He looks at literature as nature, as energy, and associates the creative process of writing with that of evolution and brings to fore the significance of imagination, especially that of metaphor: “Poems are green plants among us; if poets are suns, poems are green plants for they clearly arrest energy on its path to entropy... they help to create creativity and community”, (Glotfelty & Fromm, 1996, p. 111).

To understand nature through our imagination so that we are closer to it, and see how we are all united in nature, one could examine the work of Alexander von Humboldt, a German naturalist and explorer who believed that all aspects of the planet, from the outer atmosphere to the bottom of the oceans, were interconnected—a theory he called the “unity of nature.” “He found connections everywhere. Nothing, not even the tiniest organism, was looked at on its own.” (Wulf, 5)

In her book *The Invention of Nature* on Humboldt’s life and work, Andrea Wulf looks at nature as a concept that needs to be invented, a construct that needs creation and understanding, questioning and re-structuring. To look at nature as if we were seeing it for the first time, to measure the blueness of the sky with a cyanometer, and to think about discovering how our lives are intertwined with nature will drive us to conservation and environmental awareness. What is important is that we bring nature

into our imagination, make it a part of our fiction, and our literary understanding of the world; and only when nature and narratives are intertwined, would we feel a sense of love and reverence for it. In her book *Water and Womanhood: Religious Meanings of Rivers in Maharashtra*, Anne Feldhaus “looks at the many dimensions of cultural meanings of rivers which have existed in India”. She examines religious practices, rituals and oral traditions which are associated with rivers, allowing them to become an intrinsic part of domestic life and our cultural imagination. What brings together the work and insight of the writers and conservationists under study are the stories that emerge, the intense anthropocentric identification with nature, and the closeness to nature felt.

As environmentalism and literature intersect, the relationship between individuals and nature becomes stronger. The affinity is evident, and so is the fact that human beings are part of nature, and any separation from it would eventually be self-destructive. When this relationship is unearthed in stories, songs and myths, one can trace its journey back to the oral tradition. It is fascinating to observe that such narratives have been part of the cultural fabric of various communities. In her article ‘River of Stories’, Parineeta Dandekar unearths stories, lore, songs and poetry which depict a deep connection with the river. Autumn Peltier, in her work, evokes the archetypal connection within the womb: “Our first water teaching comes from within our own mother. We literally live in water for nine months, floating in that sacred water that gives us life.” Borgaonkar, in the novel *Nadisht*, which revolves around the constructs of the mother and the river, also states matter-of-factly right at the start: “The river is an extended womb of the mother; we suffocate when we come out of the womb. I feel like I have been reconnected to my mother’s umbilical cord when I am with the river.” Atwood’s protagonist in *Surfacing*, grappling with the idea of separation, experiences a rebirth of the self as she dives into the water. She expresses her absolute transformation: “I am not an animal or a tree, I am the thing in which the trees and animals move and grow, I am a place.” The study of these works, which are not intended to be written and read as ‘green’ literature, becomes interesting markers of the fact that it is increasingly important to read from such an ecocritical perspective, such that these debates and questions are constantly on the surface.

Writing and Praxis

Considering ecocriticism as a critical approach to literature and culture that centers around the relationships between human beings and the natural world, Glotfelty and Fromm put together concerns and questions posed by various scholars in their edited volume, *The Ecocriticism Reader*, which emerged as a reaction to

increasing unease about environmental degradation and the kind of impact human activity was having on the planet. In their introduction, they say: "What then is ecocriticism? Simply put, ecocriticism is the study of the relationship between literature and the physical environment". (Glotfelty and Fromm, xviii) According to them, one of the aspects that separates ecocriticism from other critical approaches, which limit the understanding of the 'world' to the social sphere is that "Ecocriticism expands the notion of 'the world' to include the entire ecosphere. If we agree with Barry Commoner's first law of ecology, "Everything is connected to everything else," we must conclude that literature does not float above the material world in some aesthetic ether, but, rather, plays a part in an immensely complex global system, in which energy, matter, and ideas interact." (xix) This interconnection is what becomes apparent when one considers the work done by environmentalists and writers under study within their own socio-cultural and natural environments.

Parineeta Dandekar does real work with the *South Asia Network on Dams, Rivers and People*. She brings to our notice that the river flows in our minds like consciousness, "...rivers dominate not only the landscape, but mindscapes of people and connect with us, transformed through a metaphor - deified or demonified through songs such as the *Bhatiyali*. She says, "The songs have a strange character. Because they are born on a living river with all her moods, they are not always full of praise for the river... they also talk of the drudgery of the journey, the treacherous river and its storms and floods. The metaphor of the river and the search for direction is interminable. For the boatman, the river is not just a metaphor for life; it is life itself!" Larger rivers are goddesses, whereas lesser rivers are considered to be impure, destroying settlements or even fame. Is that perhaps why one does not hesitate to pollute and destroy them?

Like Dandekar, Autumn Peltier, an 18-year-old 'water protector' and Anishinaabe Indigenous rights advocate from Ontario, Canada, is struggling to understand why, though Canada is a country of lakes and rivers, people where she is from have been given boil-water advisories. Manitoulin Island is the largest freshwater island in the world, yet people do not have access to clean drinking water. She turns water into a religion, pondering its sacredness. This deification is required to bring people out of their reverie and understand the seriousness of what it is giving us: "We are water – we come from water, and when the water is sick, we are sick."

She wants every human being to take note that "all water is original from time immemorial" and to remember that our ancestors drank from this same water thousands of years ago. She makes us perceive the living being that exists in water –

"Water not only surrounds us, but... hears us, feels us, and listens to us.... it has spirit and can feel "positive and negative thoughts." These are the stories we need to tell ourselves, the making of the metaphor, such that nature enters and stays within our imagination, understanding the unity of things, the interconnectedness of water/nature with us.

The consciousness about water and its connection with us flows from Dandekar and Peltier into the novel by Manoj Borgaonkar. Like Peltier, Borgaonkar tries to carve the interconnectedness of the river with our archetypal past in *Nadishta*. In Marathi, the pun on the title *Nadishta* would be 'naadisht', meaning someone who is obsessed with something. The narrator of the novel is unable to sever his umbilical cord to the river, especially because it would mean severing ties with his mother, who is no more. The novel is a heart-rending tale of countless people living marginalized lives outside the periphery, surrounded by various emotional and environmental concerns. It is realized out of immense devotion to the river. The stories of various characters are like the bottom of a river, which cannot be understood from its surface. The story of Saguna, a transgender individual, dominates the novel.

The narrator understands the stories of the marginalized souls he meets on the river. Their humanity and their sense of self have been rejected, and he talks to them and narrates their story. This novel equates our dysfunctional relationship with nature with that of these beings living on the margins. Since the narrator can connect deeply with nature, through the river, the trees and the monkeys, he can connect with those who have been discriminated against. Borgaonkar looks at the mother, the river and poetry as three elements of creativity.

Atwood's *Surfacing* traces her search for her nameless narrator's father, which becomes a search for her inner self, a self she discovers through nature. Though living away from society, on an island, it is a microcosm that, in fact, contains and uncovers all aspects of the larger social order. Over the course of the novel, she becomes a symbol of those who are abused and powerless. She understands her inner self only when she begins to understand nature. This novel also brings to fore the interconnectedness of beings, for instance, the trauma the narrator experiences when she sees the dead heron in a tree, is located in her ability to see nature as one whole. When she looks at the stumps of huge trees cut down, she associates her own exploitation with nature's. "The trees will never be allowed to grow that tall again, they're killed as soon as they're valuable, big trees are scarce as whales" (Atwood, 43)." She regains her sensitivity while in nature "... feeling was beginning to seep back into me, I tingled like a foot that's been asleep" (147). She also recognizes her own

creativity at the end of the novel, when her search for her parents becomes an understanding of herself as a potential creator, an acceptance of the cycle of death and rebirth. The descent into what could be perceived as psychotic, as madness, when the narrator destroys everything that belongs to the material world and wants to live in a burrow, eat plants and have a child whom she will not teach language, suggests her complete immersion into nature. The immersion into the lake, when she dives in and experiences a trance, is the moment of this complete understanding of her 'self' and what she really wants. At the novel's close, she thinks of the "shape of a goldfish now in my belly, undergoing its watery changes". (249-50).

The Need for Transnational Interconnections

In Anne Feldhaus's book, rivers have sacred qualities. They have a gender: they are female." (Courtright, 812) Her research and interpretations "point up the associations that rivers have with 'fecundity', a category that incorporates images of both fertility and death" (Sutherland, 129); and leaves us with an understanding of the 'femininity' and thereby 'fertility' of rivers rather than their ability to cleanse or make sterile. One cannot help but make ecofeminist connections that look at the denigration of rivers in the context of the denigration of women. Perhaps, with an increasing understanding of diversity, the need to accept manifold and complex definitions of the self has emerged. In the stories that Dandekar and Peltier weave around water, there is a sense of universality and diversity, which does not limit their identity as creators/females. In the work of Borgaonkar and Atwood, water becomes a space that allows for the recognition and acceptance of the self, going beyond gender alone. The collective consciousness of these environmentalist writers crosses transnational boundaries and texts, embracing the environmental concerns of all beings.

The idea of green studies is an inclusive concept that considers the intersectionality among people and in nature. Intersectional environmentalism examines the intersection of social and environmental injustices against vulnerable communities and the planet. By doing so, the self with a certain identity is obliterated; it is not just female/male, black/white, lower/higher (caste or class). It becomes a self that is a part of everything on this planet. "Intersectionality has evolved within feminist theory, and is grounded in a feminist understanding of power and knowledge production." Davis (2008, p. 68) defines intersectionality as 'the interaction between gender, race and other categories of difference in individual lives, social practices, institutional arrangements, and cultural ideologies and the outcomes of these interactions in terms of power.' Kaiser and Krosnell delve into the question of how

an intersectional study, developed alongside critical feminist theory, can, in fact, aid environmental study. They consider these interconnections as having a far-reaching impact. "Anti-racist and post-colonial commentary continues to vitalize feminist studies and, together with queer, masculinity, and disability studies, enriches the understanding of how norms are constructed and power relations interact" (Kaiser & Krosnell, 2014) and question human dominance. As one moves from ecofeminism to green studies, one goes beyond the binaries that equate power with the majority, domination with patriarchy, nature with the marginalized and a river with a woman. In the hierarchy of power, the intrinsic inequity apparent in the abuse of nature forces us to understand the patterns in these dynamics, thereby carving out ways to question and change them.

Conclusion

The presence of nature and climate change in literature has become inevitable. It will be the only way, as Amitav Ghosh states passionately in the section on stories in *The Great Derangement*: "when readers and museumgoers turn to the art and literature of our time, will they not look, first, and most urgently, for traces and portents of the altered world of their inheritance?" If it does not have a presence in art and literature, if traces of nature fade from view, if it is concealed, then, as he says, it "will come to be known as the time of the Great Derangement".

Narratives and stories bring us closer in our understanding of nature; we identify with nature as another being in the scheme of things. The work of writers and environmentalists helps us see, from the perspective of 'deep ecology', that by humanizing nature and allowing our stories to intertwine with nature's stories about itself, we can establish a spiritual connection with nature and connect with our inner selves. Reading riverine novels and unearthing stories and histories of the rivers and the people living by them, Dandekar laments: "And here, I'm left wondering that in the absence of a gentle river, how many epiphanies have I lost? Would I be a different, wiser, happier person if the rivers of my land also flowed like Ichhamati once did?" As we loop back to the first quote: "The answer lies in Recognition – a passage from ignorance to knowledge" (Ghosh, 2016) and translating it into "the medium of one's imagination" – into stories.

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